

sonus, an open-source Max/MSP package for sound experimentation and algorithmic composition

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ABSTRACT

This paper introduces *sonus*, an open-source Max/MSP package comprising a collection of C++ externals developed with Cycling '74 Min-DevKit. The package is designed to support practices in algorithmic and AI-assisted composition, experimental sound synthesis and creative sound design. Its objects are organised into four categories: generators, including various kinds of oscillators and modulation sources; effects and sample manipulation, implementing real-time effects and offline processing of audio buffers; neural networks and AI, featuring implementations of some autonomous generative systems; math and utilities, providing functions to ease common computational tasks. The package also includes a set of Max for Live devices that demonstrate practical integrations of selected externals in compositional workflows. *sonus* is released under the MIT license and publicly available on GitHub.

1 INTRODUCTION

Algorithmic composition and experimental sound design take on multiple facets in contemporary electroacoustic music practice, manifesting in a rich diversity of approaches, ranging from rule-based generative systems and stochastic processes to real-time interactive environments and machine learning-driven sonic architectures [1, 2, 3, 4, 5]. While certain algorithmic methods predate the invention of computers by centuries, their adoption expanded significantly with the advent of digital computation, eventually extending beyond academic contexts into popular music practices.

Among the most used tools for developing custom pipelines for composition and sound creation and processing, Cycling '74 Max/MSP holds a special place, due to its relative ease of use (at least compared to text-based solutions) and its vast ecosystem, made up of numerous third-party packages that extend the functionalities provided by its built-in objects.

Thus, developing a series of external objects for Max/MSP is an effective way to expand the possibilities of music creation, enabling seamless integration with other developers' packages and creative tools. In this paper, an open-source Max/MSP package called *sonus* is presented, featuring a wide range of external objects designed for sound experimentation and algorithmic composition.

2 PACKAGE STRUCTURE

The externals in the *sonus* package are organised into four categories:

- *Generators*: a set of externals that produce signals using various algorithms, from bytebeat generators and strange attractors to more widely adopted approaches in mainstream digital synthesis. Most of these can serve as sources for both audio and modulation signals.
- *Effects and sample manipulation*: a collection of externals that apply effects either to an incoming signal or to

a buffer (depending on the object), making them suitable for both real-time and non-realtime sound design.

- *Neural networks and AI*: a range of externals dedicated to artificial intelligence and generative algorithms, including cellular automata, genetic algorithms, L-systems, and deep learning.
- *Math and utilities*: a series of externals ranging from convenient utilities to mathematical functions, helping to reduce the number of objects required for recurring operations.

Additionally, the package includes a series of Max for Live devices built around selected externals, demonstrating practical use cases within an actual compositional environment.

3 IMPLEMENTATION

3.1 Previous and similar works

There is a wide range of Max/MSP packages that cover one or more aspects *sonus* deals with, and a complete review of such packages is beyond the scope of the current paper. As far as the machine learning and autonomous systems are concerned, some notable and currently maintained examples include *FluCoMa* [6], *ml.star* [7], and *dada* [8], while for algorithmic and math-based composition there are packages like *RTC-lib*, *MuBu* [9], *Upshot*, and *bach* [10].

Max/MSP is not the only environment where algorithmic composition is possible: other notable examples, let alone the direct use of general purpose programming languages with specific libraries, are OpenMusic [11], Pure Data, CSound, Chuck [12], SuperCollider [13], and Iannix [14].

3.2 Development

The rationale behind *sonus* is to provide an environment comprising objects that span a continuum from high-level, composition-

and structure-oriented tools to low-level sound generators, processors, and utility objects that bridge the two domains. Moreover, the package consists entirely of externals coded in C++, deliberately avoiding abstractions and Gen-based objects to ensure both optimal performance and architectural homogeneity.

Cycling '74 Min-DevKit¹, a C++ wrapper around C-based Max SDK, was used to develop all the externals. Some externals also rely on additional libraries, namely *muParserX*² for parsing the bytebeat expressions, *SouTeL* library³ for most of DSP algorithms and public domain *dj_fft*⁴ for FFT analysis and resynthesis of buffer contents.

The Max for Live devices have been developed following the Max for Live production guidelines⁵ by Ableton.

Source code and compiled externals for Windows and macOS are available on GitHub: <https://github.com/valeriorlandini/sonus>. *sonus* source code is released under MIT license⁶.

4 USE CASES

The externals featured in *sonus* package can be employed in different scenarios and integrated in a series of workflows, including:

Algorithmic composition Algorithmic processes in composition are made possible at different levels: from the macrostructural one, through the implementation of different generative and autonomous systems (more on this in the following section), to the microstructural, taking advantage of externals designed for complex modulations and sound generation built upon mathematical models.

Sound design Several externals are dedicated to sound generation and processing, implementing operations both on real-time audio and on buffers and overlapping their use cases on those of algorithmic composition. Objects working on buffers can operate on an arbitrary number of channels, making them suitable for multichannel sound design and editing.

Education The externals dealing with autonomous systems and artificial intelligence have been also conceived to be used in an educational framework, allowing to exemplify how famous algorithms work under the hood. In a few cases, like *sonus.dnn* that emulates a deep neural network, the main aim is educational, leaving an optimized but opaque implementation of the same system to other packages. Moreover, since all the code is open source and MIT licensed, the code itself can be an educational resource not only about the implementation of the algorithms, but also about how Cycling '74 Min-DevKit can be used in a wide range of situations.

Workflow shortcuts Some externals implement DSP and math routines that can also be achieved with stock Max/MSP objects, but with the necessity of using different objects to obtain the same output that a single (and C++ optimized) *sonus* external can return. This does not only apply to most of the objects of the math and utilities category, but also to some oscillators and effects.

5 SELECTED IN-DEPTH EXTERNALS DESCRIPTIONS

To better exemplify the concept and the implementation details behind the package, some selected externals will be explained in-depth.

5.1 *sonus.bufx*

This external allows to make a series of manipulations on a buffer consisting of any number of channels. Transformations that can be applied belong to different domains:

- Classic audio effects, like filters, distortion, reverb, delay, ring modulation, etc.
- Mixing and extending the current buffer with another one.
- Time stretching (with pitch change).
- Fade in and out.
- Audio transformations in the frequency domain.

Transformations are applied by sending messages formatted in the style of [transformation] [parameters (if needed)]. If the syntax is ill-formed, a proper error message is outputted to the Max console.

A function allows to take a snapshot of the current buffer content so that it can be recovered later. If multiple snapshots of the same buffer are needed, the external *sonus.bufsnap* can be used to achieve this.

5.2 *sonus.bytebeat~*

Bytebeat is a term referring to a particular technique of generating raw PCM audio with short C-style expressions, typically involving bitwise operations, arithmetic, and logical operators, which are evaluated at audio sample rates. It was first introduced in this form in 2011 by Ville-Matias Heikkila [15]. In a bytebeat expression there is typically a variable *t* that represents the monotonically increasing sample index and it usually goes from 0 to 255. This variable can appear multiple times, so that it can be manipulated in different ways, thus obtaining a certain development of the sequence. For example, `t*((t>12)|(t>8))&(63&(t>4))` is a valid and typical bytebeat formula.

The external *sonus.bytebeat~* allows the user to specify any bytebeat formula and listen to the result. The parsing is carried out by the library *muParserX*, and there is the possibility to select a certain sampling rate reduction (up to a factor of 10) so that the pitch is adjusted accordingly. There is also a LFO mode: when activated the sampling rate is further reduced by a factor of 50 and the output is lowpassed, making it suitable as a modulation source.

¹<https://github.com/Cycling74/min-devkit>

²<https://beltoforion.de/en/muparserx>

³<https://github.com/valeriorlandini/soutel>

⁴https://github.com/jdupuy/dj_fft

⁵<https://github.com/Ableton/maxdevtools>

⁶<https://opensource.org/licenses/mit>

There is also another similar external, `sonus.byteplay~`, that allows to explore a selection of fifteen famous bytebeat formulas.

5.3 `sonus.ca`

A cellular automaton is a mathematical model used to describe the evolution of discrete complex systems, studied across various scientific fields including biology, physics, mathematics, and computer science [16, 17]. A cellular automaton system consists of a grid of cells (finite or infinite in size, with any number of spatial dimensions), where each cell contains an automaton that can assume a finite number of states (in its simplest form, *alive* or *dead*). Each configuration of the entire grid is referred to as a *generation*, and the transition to the next generation is governed by evolution rules that depend on the current state of each automaton and those of its neighbouring cells. Depending on the chosen rules and the initial configuration, the system can exhibit vastly different behaviours, from complete extinction to unbounded expansion, including static patterns or oscillating structures.

`sonus.ca` implements a system of 2D, two states, cellular automata of arbitrary size, and is designed to be manipulated and projected using a `matrixctrl` object, even if operations through messages only, without involving a matrix, are supported. Rules for birth and survival can be set by the user (and also changed during the system life cycle) and a series of additional functions can randomly initialize the system with a certain population or mutate the states of a part of it. `sonus.ca` output is formatted so that it is easily linkable to a matrix control, as exemplified in the included help patch (figure 1).

Figure 1: `sonus.ca` in action, from the help patch.

A system like this can have multiple use cases, for it can fit basically any scenario where a non-trivial, but rule-based, evolutionary model is needed. The direct link to a `matrixctrl` is not only an aid to visualization using a standard Max object, but can be used for creative control of matrices.

Cellular automata are also found in `sonus.ecaosc~` external, which implements an oscillator using an elementary cellular

automaton [18], a 1D system with 256 configurations, corresponding to the rule table defined over the eight possible neighbourhood states of a cell and its two neighbours. The user can specify a configuration and an initial state (of a matrix with eight cells), and at each step the system status is interpreted as a binary number then scaled inside $[-1.0, 1.0]$ range. `sonus.ecaosc~` is particularly suited for modulation signals.

5.4 `sonus.cryptoverb~`

`sonus.cryptoverb~` is an algorithmic stereo reverberation effect which is based on four blocks:

- **Block 1:** Four comb filters with different settings for each channel. The first two filters process the input in series; their output is then fed both into the next two comb filters (also in series) and mixed with the output of those third and fourth filters. Additionally, the output of the first two combs is mixed with that of the other channel. Finally, each channel's output is filtered with a biquad lowpass filter.
- **Block 2:** The structure is identical to Block 1, but the comb filters use different values for delay, gain, feed-forward, and feedback.
- **Block 3:** Four allpass filters in series per channel, with the delay time of the third allpass continuously modulated by a sinusoidal LFO.
- **Block 4:** Six allpass filters in series per channel, with the delay times of the third and sixth filters continuously modulated by a low-frequency random signal.

These blocks can be arranged in three distinct configurations:

- **Parallel processing:** The input signal is processed simultaneously by all four blocks, and their individual outputs (per channel) are then mixed together.
- **Serial processing:** The input signal passes sequentially through each block, one after another.
- **Hybrid processing:** The input first passes through blocks 3 and 4 in series; the resulting signal is then split and processed in parallel by blocks 1 and 2, with their outputs finally mixed together.

Each configuration produces a distinct timbral character, and can be chosen with a dedicated option in the external. Whichever configuration is set, a master lowpass filter, with adjustable cutoff frequency, is applied to the resulting signal. Other customizable parameters include the wet amount of each block and the overall wet amount of the effect.

5.5 `sonus.ga`

A genetic algorithm is a heuristic process that, using the evolutionary concepts of mutation, crossover, and natural selection, aims to optimize a solution to a problem [19]. In other words, a genetic algorithm performs a series of iterations on the material (the *population*) to be optimized, which may consist, among other things, of collections of alphanumeric sequences, algorithms, sets of images, etc., and at each iteration the material is evaluated with a score (called *fitness*). By combining elements

from the population (*crossover*), randomly altering some of their parts (*mutation*), and discarding lower-scoring individuals in favour of newly generated ones with higher scores (*selection*), the algorithm progressively approaches, through the fittest individuals in the population, an optimal solution to the problem. A perfect solution is not guaranteed to exist; therefore, a satisfactory threshold is usually defined, or alternatively a maximum number of iterations is set, beyond which the obtained result can be considered acceptable.

`sonus.ga` implements a genetic algorithm capable of generating a target sequence of symbols starting from a dictionary of allowed tokens and a specified population size. At each iteration, the sequences of the population (which are initialized randomly) are crossed and mutated and the sequences closest to the desired target are kept. Such sequences can be used for multiple purposes, such as to drive a sequencer or to control the parameters of a synthesizer. Another external, `sonus.ga.num`, uses the same algorithm but generates a list of numbers within a specified range.

5.6 `sonus.linden`

An L-system (named after its inventor Aristid Lindenmayer) is a type of formal grammar consisting in a model that, starting from an initial statement (the *axiom*) along with a set of variables and possibly some constants, iteratively rewrites the statement by applying substitution rules simultaneously to all its elements [20]. For example, a simple system might consist of the variables A and B, the axiom A, and the substitution rules $A \rightarrow AB$ and $B \rightarrow A$. This would produce a sequence such as: $A \rightarrow AB \rightarrow ABA \rightarrow ABAAB \rightarrow ABAABABA$, and so on. Constants are symbols that do not evolve, so basically their rule is $C \rightarrow C$. Such a system can generate complex tree-like structures, especially when successive states are placed one after another and constants are introduced to control the direction of growth.

`sonus.linden` is an external that implements a classic L-system with some additional options. Its core capabilities provide the possibility of setting the axiom and a set of rules, and then evolving the string each time a bang is received. Variables and constants are deduced from the rules. The resulting output can be used, like that of `sonus.ga`, to alter the parameters of any programmable part of a patch.

The external also implements a probability parameter, which allows substitutions to occur only some of the time, thus creating a basic stochastic L-system. In addition to this, more than one rule (separated by a `|` symbol) can be specified for the same item: in this case, one of the possible rules is selected each time randomly, with each rule having the same probability to be chosen. Moreover, the sequence can be truncated so that only the last n symbols, with n selectable by the user, are kept. This technically breaks the definition of a standard L-system, but can be useful in use cases that require a fixed number of parameters (e.g. to drive a sequencer or to change the settings of a synthesizer).

5.7 `sonus.lorenz~` and `sonus.roessler~`

Chaotic systems are complex mathematical models that exhibit extreme sensitivity to initial conditions. At first glance, the

variables associated with such a system may appear to evolve entirely at random. In reality, however, their behaviour is governed by precise mathematical functions. What makes these functions particularly powerful is their ability to produce drastically different outcomes in response to even imperceptibly small perturbations, a property that renders chaotic systems exceptionally well-suited for simulating the complexity observed in natural phenomena and living organisms. Some attractors (i.e. sets of states toward which a dynamical system evolves over time) exhibit chaotic behaviour for specific parameter values. This results in an apparently unpredictable development known as a strange attractor. Two of the most widely studied examples of such systems are the Lorenz [21] and Rössler [22] systems, which have also found notable use in algorithmic composition [23].

`sonus.lorenz~` and `sonus.roessler~` implement the attractors related to these two systems. Both have three variables that evolve in a continuous way, according to these equations for the Lorenz system:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dx}{dt} = \sigma(y - x) \\ \frac{dy}{dt} = x(\rho - z) - y \\ \frac{dz}{dt} = xy - \beta z. \end{cases}$$

And these for the Rössler system:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dx}{dt} = -y - z \\ \frac{dy}{dt} = x + ay \\ \frac{dz}{dt} = b + z(x - c) \end{cases}$$

The outputs of these two externals provide three signals corresponding to the x , y , and z components (Lorenz outputs exemplified in figure 2). An evolution speed parameter controls how far the system advances from one sample to the next, effectively acting as a frequency control. The system's constants can be adjusted within ranges that yield a strange attractor. The outputs exhibit rich timbral qualities, making them well-suited for drones and evolving textures, but they are especially effective as modulation signals.

Figure 2: Oscilloscope view of Lorenz attractor outputs.

Other objects that can generate chaotic sequences are `sonus.logistic` and `sonus.tent`, which implement logistic [24] and tent maps respectively.

5.8 `sonus.neurosc~`

`sonus.neurosc~` is a wavetable oscillator based on a deep neural network (specifically, an autoencoder) trained on a dataset of 15,000 waveforms. The model employs an eight-dimensional latent space, and its decoder consists of a single fully connected

layer with a *tanh* activation function, mapping the eight latent coordinates directly to the 600 sample points of the output waveform. A deeper architecture with multiple nonlinear layers is avoided, both for performance reasons and to ensure that any gradual trajectory through the latent space yields smooth, continuous and differentiable interpolations in the waveform domain.

The external is implemented as a conventional wavetable oscillator, but with the capability of modulating each of the eight inputs to the latent space via messages or signals, enabling the generation of complex and dynamically evolving waveforms.

This kind of decoder, trained with the same dataset but with a slightly different architecture on its encoder counterpart, also powers the web application *NeuralWavetables*⁷, that can be used to interactively explore the latent space and save the resulting single cycle waveforms as audio files.

The generated waveform can be optionally windowed (using a Hann function). In any case, to avoid clicks and other artefacts the first and last 30 samples are interpolated and the output lowpassed with a Butterworth filter with very low resonance and a cutoff at 16000 Hz (or, for sample rates lower than 44100 Hz, 70% the Nyquist frequency).

5.9 *sonus.nowave~*

sonus.nowave~ is an experiment to explore the Mersenne Twister pseudo-random generator `mt19937` of the C++ standard library. The external consists in a wavetable oscillator of a certain size (specified by the user) resembling a ramp. According to the requested seed, the generator is passed to `std::shuffle` together with the unscrambled waveform. The result is a new shape, where the steps are arranged in a new order.

This simple architecture allows to generate millions of different shapes, with the possibility to recall any of them just by using its corresponding seed. With waveforms of very small size a well-defined and rather harmonic timbre can be obtained (especially if interpolation option is on), while larger waveforms present harsh and drone-like textures.

5.10 *sonus.pulsar~*

Pulsar synthesis is a granular synthesis technique proposed by Curtis Roads [25], which consists in producing periodic signals, of length p , made up of a waveform of length d and a silence of length s , with $p = d + s$. The waveform can be of any shape, and an envelope (like a window function or an ADSR-style function) can be applied. A particular effect can be achieved by modulating d while keeping p (so the overall frequency) constant, a technique that Roads calls *pulsaret-width modulation*.

sonus.pulsar~ implements a pulsar oscillator with adjustable frequency (thus controlling p), duty cycle (i.e. d length, as a proportion on the total length of the cycle), selectable waveform and envelope (chosen among a series of window functions plus linear and exponential decays).

The pulsar oscillator has interesting timbral features, and with sufficiently small values for d it can also be used with infrasonic frequencies, resulting in clicky textures that can become glitchy if frequency and duty cycle are randomly modulated. *sonus.pulsar~* is also a good source for modulation signals.

Moreover, if the duty cycle is set to 1.0 and the window function to rectangular, *sonus.pulsar~* can be used as a regular wavetable oscillator with different shapes.

5.11 *sonus.wavesets*

This external implements a series of sound manipulation techniques based on the concept of wavesets, as outlined by Trevor Wishart [25, 26]. A waveset is a portion of audio delimited by two consecutive zero-crossings, so it can be partially assimilated to a waveform cycle, even if the two concepts do not always overlap.

sonus.wavesets identifies the wavesets of a specified buffer and allows a series of operations either on each single waveset or on a group of consecutive wavesets, whose number is decided by the user. Currently implemented manipulations include stretching, shuffling, muting, substitution with simple waveforms (e.g. sine, saw, square), filtering, in addition to various other operations. Like in *sonus.buffx*, a function allows to take a snapshot of the current buffer content so that it can be recovered later if the applied transformations do not satisfy the composer.

6 MAX FOR LIVE DEVICES

In addition to the externals, the package includes six Max for Live devices that use some of the *sonus* objects and show how they can be integrated in a higher level framework.

The included devices are:

- *Bitman*: An effect built around *sonus.bitman~*, that quantizes the input signal to 8-bit resolution and then allows each individual bit to be independently toggled, set, cleared, or left unchanged. Editing the most significant bits produces pronounced distortion and marked waveshaping effects, while modifying only the least significant bits results in subtle, nuanced alterations to the original signal.
- *Byter*: This device is built around *sonus.bytebeat~*, a sound generator based on bytebeat algorithms (described in the previous section). It features two independent bytebeat generators, each accepting user-defined formulas and offering a selection of presets (figure 3). The outputs of the two generators can be mixed, and their playback rates are adjustable, extending into the infrasonic range, which enables their use as modulation signals. An optional complementary reverb, implemented via *sonus.cryptoverb~*, can be applied to the dry mix.
- *Cryptoverb*: This effect wraps *sonus.cryptoverb~* (a stereo algorithmic reverberator described in the previous section) with an accessible and intuitive user

⁷<https://valeriorlandini.github.io/neuralwavetables/>

interface, while preserving all the options of the underlying external.

- **Modallator:** This device is a modulator that enables the design of complex waveforms by mixing different generators (figure 4). Namely, *Modallator* encapsulates six oscillators:
 - *Random shape oscillator:* A non bandlimited oscillator, designed for LFOs, with a waveform that changes periodically. It uses `sonus.rsosc~`.
 - *Additive oscillator:* An additive oscillator with gain and phase control for each harmonic, implemented in `sonus.harmosc~`. In this device, the gains of the first four harmonics are adjustable.
 - *Phase distortion oscillator:* A typical phase distortion oscillator, as implemented in `sonus.pdosc~`.
 - *Virtual analog oscillator:* A virtual analog bandlimited oscillator with four shapes that can be mixed: sine, triangle, saw and square. It uses `sonus.vaosc~`.
 - *Pulsar oscillator:* Pulsar oscillator using `sonus.pulsar~`, described in the previous section.
 - *Custom wavetable oscillator:* A wavetable oscillator whose waveform can be specified with a list of numbers, e.g. coming from a `multislider` object. It uses `sonus.nwosc~`.

Each oscillator can be turned on or off and some of its parameters can be adjusted. The device is completed by a section that resembles the one of the stock Ableton LFO device, thus allowing to choose LFO frequency (with the beat sync option), deviation, smoothness, steps, jitter and offset.

- **Pulsynthe:** An eight-voice polyphonic synthesizer based on two pulsar oscillators (implemented with `sonus.pulsar~`). The synth also includes a filter (using a biquad multimode filter implemented in `sonus.biquads~`), three ADSR envelopes (for amplitude, pitch, and filter cutoff), and the ability to combine the two oscillators by mixing them, through ring modulation, or using AND or OR bitwise operators.
- **StrangeLFO:** A LFO modulator device built around the two strange attractors described in the previous section, `sonus.lorenz~` and `sonus.roessler~`. The parameters of the two attractors can be adjusted, as well as the prominence of each of them in the final mix and how they should be mixed. The device can also be used as audio generator, with an optional reverb (that uses `sonus.cryptoverb~`) to design dense drones.

Figure 3: *Byter* device.

Figure 4: *Modallator* device.

Additionally, all Max for Live devices incorporate externals from the math and utilities category to simplify recurring tasks and streamline device design.

7 CONCLUSIONS

This paper introduced *sonus*, an open-source Max/MSP package comprising C++ externals oriented toward algorithmic composition, autonomous systems and creative sound design based on mathematical models. Key use cases were discussed, and some externals were examined in depth, selected from those that best exemplify the package’s features and underlying conceptual framework.

Owing to its eclectic yet coherent design philosophy, *sonus* can be employed across diverse compositional scenarios and at various levels of the compositional hierarchy, either as a self-contained ecosystem or, more effectively, in integration with the broader ecosystem of Max/MSP packages.

A series of Max for Live devices included in the package demonstrates how its components can be applied within a conventional DAW workflow for modulation, synthesis, and sound processing, thereby embedding algorithmic practices into more mainstream approaches to music production.

Future development of *sonus* will focus on expanding the range and capabilities of its externals, alongside a curated set of examples and tutorials that, complementing the existing help patches, will mitigate the learning curve and fully realize its educational potential. A further objective is the creation of a cohesive and extended suite of Max for Live devices, establishing *sonus* as the foundation for a comprehensive line of drag-and-drop creative tools.

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